

STUDY ON THE RHEOLOGY AND TENSILE PROPERTY OF CCF300/PEEK COMPOSITES VIA POWDER IMPREGNATION METHOD

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Keywords: Thermoplastic, Powder impregnation, Rheology, Mechanical property

ABSTRACT

With the advent of high performance thermoplastic polymers, structural applications for thermoplastic composites are increasing rapidly. Thermoplastic matrix composites possess distinct advantages compared with thermoset matrix composites in terms of recyclability, high specific strength and specific stiffness, corrosion resistance, enhanced impact toughness. Nowadays, the number of material forms and combinations in carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic polymers has increased exponentially, leading to expanding application avenues in automotive, transportation, marine, aerospace, mass transit, military and construction sectors. Powder impregnation is identified in this paper as a suitable technique for the manufacture of thermoplastic prepreg. This technique is based on the powder coating technique, which exhibits a fine dispersion of polymer particles in the fiber tow in which the PEEK particles are equably deposited onto the fiber surface.

This paper presents an experimental investigation about the influence of resin's rheology property and tensile strength on the mechanical properties of CCF300 reinforced PEEK composites via powder impregnation method. Accurately, carbon fiber CCF300 (Weihai Expansion Fiber Co., Ltd.) was mainly made of unidirectional yarns consisting of 3000 filaments with diameter of about 7 μm each. Two kinds of PEEK with different rheology properties and mechanical properties were produced from ICI (Victrex 150P), and Changchun Jilin University Special Plastic Engineering Research Co., Ltd. (in powder form), respectively, which are numbered uniformly in turn, that is, PEEK1 and PEEK2.

In order to manufacture CCF300/PEEK composites, it is necessary to analyze resin's rheology behavior and basic mechanical property by a comparative study. The rheology behaviors of both resins are shown below.

Figure 1: MFR versus Pressure profiles for different PEEK: (a) PEEK1, (b) PEEK2

It can be observed that MFR versus Pressure profiles present a non-linear relationship. And the MFR of PEEK1 at 390 °C and 400 °C are much higher than those of PEEK2, which predicts that PEEK1 has a lower viscosity.

The optical images shown below confirmed the prediction that the impregnation states of composites depends on the viscosity of resins to a large extent.

Figure 2: The impregnation states of two resins with carbon fiber CCF300
(a) PEEK1, (b) PEEK2

Furthermore, these PEEK samples were cut into standard sizes for tensile testing based on ASTM D 638. The tensile strength of PEEK1 is 92.56 MPa, and the tensile strength of PEEK2 is 99.71 MPa.

Apparently, the rheology behavior and tensile property of these resins are quite different. So the tensile property of composites made by carbon fiber CCF300 and those resins can reflect which element plays the most significant role on basic mechanical property of composites.

The CCF300 reinforced PEEK laminated plates are made in vacuum assisted hot-pressing machine with variable parameters at 400 °C. And the tensile testing results based on ASTM D3039 showed below. And it can be observed that the tensile property of CCF300/PEEK1 composites are much better.

Figure 3: The tensile test results of CCF300/PEEK1 and CCF300/PEEK2 composites

In summary, we have conducted a comprehensive study on the influence of viscosity and tensile strength of resin matrixes on the basic mechanical property of composites. The result shows that the viscosity plays a more significant role on the tensile property of composites because of its decisive effect on the impregnation states of laminated plates.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express their gratitude towards the Laboratory of Polymer Matrix Composites, Beihang University, for the support of this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] Vaidya U K, Chawla K K. Processing of fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites[J]. *International Materials Reviews*, 2008, 53(4):185-218.
- [2] Rath M, Kreuzberger S, Hinrichsen G. Manufacture of aramid fibre reinforced nylon-12 by dry powder impregnation process[J]. *Composites Part A Applied Science & Manufacturing*, 1998, 29(8):933-938.
- [3] Xiao X R, Hiel C C, Cardon A H. Characterization and modeling of nonlinear viscoelastic response of PEEK resin and PEEK composites ☆ [J]. *Composites Engineering*, 1994, 4(7):681-702.
- [4] Marduel J. Device and method for impregnating a porous material with powder: EP, CA 2728961 A1[P]. 2010.
- [5] Caramaro L, Marduel J. Process for producing a stampable reinforced composite semi-finished product[J]. Wipo, 2013.
- [6] Hayes B S, Seferis J C. The effect of fabric tension and the number of impregnation rollers on woven fabric prepreg quality and cured laminates[J]. *Composites Part A Applied Science & Manufacturing*, 1997, 28(9-10):791-799.
- [7] Gibson A G, Månson J A. Impregnation technology for thermoplastic matrix composites[J]. *Composites Manufacturing*, 1992, 3(4):223-233.
- [8] Katouzian M, Bruller O S, Horoschenkoff A. On the Effect of Temperature on the Creep Behavior of Neat and Carbon Fiber Reinforced PEEK and Epoxy Resin[J]. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1995, 29(3):372-387.
- [9] Lee W I, Springer G S. A Model of the Manufacturing Process of Thermoplastic Matrix Composites[J]. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1987, 21(11):1017-1055.
- [10] Bernhardsson J, Shishoo R. Effect of Processing Parameters on Consolidation Quality of GF/PP Commingled Yarn Based Composites[J]. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 2000, 13(4):292-313.
- [11] Miller A, Wei C, Gibson A G. Manufacture of polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) matrix composites via the powder impregnation route[J]. *Composites Part A Applied Science & Manufacturing*, 1996, 27(1):49-56.
- [12] Liu X, Zhu Z, Kang G, et al. Experimental study on uniaxial time-dependent cyclic character of carbon fiber reinforced PEEK resin matrix composite[J]. *Fuhe Cailiao Xuebao/acta Materiae Compositae Sinica*, 2012, 29(1):28-34.
- [13] Bafna S S, Baird D G. An Impregnation Model for the Preparation of Thermoplastic Prepregs[J]. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1992, 26(5):683-707.
- [14] Stavrov V P, Stavrov V V, Pankova N V, et al. Variation of the structure and permeability of tensioned fiber layers during impregnation with a thermoplastic polymer melt[J]. *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, 2000, 36(2):155-162.
- [15] Sharma M, Bijwe J, Mitschang P. Wear performance of PEEK-carbon fabric composites with strengthened fiber-matrix interface[J]. *Wear*, 2011, 271(9-10):2261-2268.
- [16] Steggall-Murphy C, Simacek P, Advani S G, et al. A model for thermoplastic melt impregnation of fiber bundles during consolidation of powder-impregnated continuous fiber composites[J]. *Composites Part A Applied Science & Manufacturing*, 2010, 41(1):93-100.
- [17] Rath M, Kreuzberger S, Hinrichsen G. Manufacture of aramid fibre reinforced nylon-12 by dry powder impregnation process[J]. *Composites Part A Applied Science & Manufacturing*, 1998, 29(8):933-938.
- [18] Camanho P P, Davila C G, De Moura M F. Numerical Simulation of Mixed-Mode Progressive Delamination in Composite Materials[J]. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2003, 37(16):1415-1438.
- [19] Khatri S C. Mechanical property enhancement of thicker section thermoplastic composites by hybridization[J]. 1990.
- [20] Friedrich K, Gogeva T, Fakirov S. Thermoplastic impregnated fiber bundles: Manufacturing of laminates and fracture mechanics characterization[J]. *Composites Science & Technology*, 1988, 33(2):97-120.